

Physico-chemical Studies on Metal Chelates of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneanil (HMAA)

Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 6 May 1978, revised 28 August 1978,
accepted 22 December 1978

IN continuation of our previous communications^{2,3}, herein we describe potentiometric studies on complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneanil (HMAA) with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Mn(II) and Cd(II) at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$ in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at constant ionic strength maintained by adding 0.1M KNO₃. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{4,5} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹ has been applied to determine the protonation constant of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log K values were computed by various computational methods. The proton-ligand stability constants determined by interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values method and metal-ligand stability constants determined by least square method are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGAND AND METAL COMPLEXES

Ion	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
H	10.83	3.57	14.40
Cu(II)	8.22	6.43	14.65
Ni(II)	7.05	5.21	12.26
Co(II)	6.42	4.37	10.79
Zn(II)	7.83	5.40	13.23
Mn(II)	5.62	4.11	9.63
Cd(II)	7.74	5.30	13.04

From the values of stability constant of the metal chelates the order is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. This is in accordance with Irving and Williams order⁶. A parallelism between log K and second ionization potential of the metal ions was also observed, as had been suggested by Irving and Williams⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Department of Chemistry for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for providing the scholarship to one of us (Y.Z.P.).

References

1. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
2. Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI, *J. Inst. of Chemists (India)*, (in press).
3. Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI, *J. I. C. S.* (in press).
4. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen.
5. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3129.

Colorimetric Estimation of Vanadium(V) with N-o-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic Acid

(Miss) S. K. AGRAWAL and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University,
Raipur, 492.002, M. P.

Manuscript received 7 April 1977, revised 26 April 1978,
accepted 22 December 1978

N-ARYLHYDROXAMIC acids are being increasingly used as selective and sensitive reagent for vanadium(V) and other metal ions¹⁻³. It is well known that introduction of an electrophilic substituent like chlorine on the N-phenyl ring of a reagent (N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid) reduces the stability of the metal complexes and thus increases the selectivity of the reagent¹⁰⁻¹¹. Hence N-o-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid has been synthesised and examined for the colorimetric estimation of vanadium(V) and it was found as a selective and sensitive reagent for vanadium(V). The method has been applied for the determination of vanadium(V) in B.C.S. steel.

Experimental

N-o-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic Acid: The reagent was prepared from N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine and cinnamoylchloride by the reported method¹². All attempts to obtain N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in solid state failed. Hence the hydroxylamine was prepared *in situ* and the ligand was synthesised by the earlier reported method¹³⁻¹⁴. It melted at 183° and gave the following analysis: Found N 4.84%, calcd. N 5.11%.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of the reagent in ethanol, free chloroform, was used for all extraction work.

Standard Vanadium Solution: A stock solution of vanadium was prepared from analytical grade ammonium metavanadate by standard method.

Foreign Ions Solution: The solutions of foreign ions were prepared from reagent grade salts following the procedure of West¹⁵.

Apparatus: A Carl Zeiss UV VIS Specord and C. Z. Spekol with 10 mm matched silica cells were employed for absorbance measurements.

General Procedure: An aliquot of the standard vanadium solution containing 0.02-0.2 mg vanadium(V) was transferred into a separatory funnel and the acidity was adjusted between 4 to 7M with hydrochloric acid. 10 ml of the reagent solution was added and vanadium(V) was extracted into chloroform by the reported method⁶. Absorbance was measured at 550 nm against chloroform as a blank.

* To whom correspondence should be made.

Results

Effect of Acidity : The maximum colour intensity was obtained in the range of 4 to 7M hydrochloric acid medium.

Effect of Reagent : The absorbance increased rapidly as the mole-ratio of reagent to vanadium increased from 1 : 1 to 6 : 1. Above this ratio (up to 100 : 1) the absorbance was practically the same.

The colour system was found stable for 24 hours and the order of mixing of reagent was not critical.

Beer's Law : Beer's law is obeyed from concentration range of 1.50 to 5.50 ppm.

Effect of Foreign Ions : The ions listed below do not interfere even when the weight ratio of each to vanadium was 200 : 1.

Li(I), K(I), Cu(II), Ag(I), Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), U(VI), Pb(II), Cd(II), As(III), Ti(IV), borate, oxalate, fluoride and ammonium. However, Zr(IV), Ce(IV), Mo(VI), and W(VI) interfere.

Titanium(IV) interferes with PBHA but it does not interfere with N-*o*-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid.

Determination of Vanadium in Steel : Vanadium was determined in B.C.S. steel. The steel solutions were prepared by the reported method¹⁶⁻¹⁷. The results of the analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN B.C.S. STEEL

B.C.S. Steel No.	Vanadium found %	Certified value %V
64a alloy steel	1.545	1.57
241/1 high speed steel	1.540	1.57
252 alloy steel	0.450	0.46

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing facilities. One of them (Miss S. K. A.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of a fellowship.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR, "N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1972.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and B. K. PAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 43.
3. S. P. BHARGAVA and N. C. SOGANI, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1971, **255**, 36.
4. D. C. BHURA and S. G. TANDON, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **53**, 379.

5. P. MURUGAIYAN, "Complexes of Cerium with Substituted Benzohydroxamic Acids", M.Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1966.
6. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **66**, 39.
7. H. L. KAPOOR, Y. K. AGRAWAL and P. C. VERMA, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 193.
8. B. K. PAL, B. K. MITRA and S. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 554.
9. ABBASI, A. SHAHID, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **48**, 714.
10. U. TANDON and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 583.
11. S. G. TANDON and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 583.
12. U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12**, 143.
13. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 753.
14. A. K. MAJUMDAR and GAYATRI DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 147.
15. P. W. WRST, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1941, **18**, 528.
16. F. D. SNELL and G. T. SNELL, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc. New York, 1949, Vol. II, Chapter 24.
17. S. G. CLARKE, *Analyst*, 1927, **52**, 466.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Nickel(II) with Thiosalicylidene Ethylenediimine*

A. R. SAPLE and D. N. PATKAR

Chemistry Department, University of Bombay, Bombay-400098

Manuscript received 27 June 1978, revised 20 October 1978; accepted 22 December 1978

In the present paper, the reaction of thiosalen with nickel(II) has been utilised to develop a new sensitive method for determination of traces of nickel.

Thiosalen reacts with Ni(II) in weakly acidic medium to form a purple red complex which is soluble in aqueous acetone medium containing $\geq 60\%$ acetone. This reaction enables detection of up to 0.2 μg of Ni by the spot test technique.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm cells. An Elico Li-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements. Thiosalen was prepared by the method of Beck¹. The chloroform solution of the reagent obtained was standardised by titration with a standard lead tetracetate solution in acetic acid medium using quinizarin indicator according to the method recommended by Verma and Bose² for mercaptans. A concentrated ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) solution of the reagent was used

* Paper presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Bangalore, December 12-15, 1976.